

SHUDDHA CHIKITSA AND PHARMACOVIGILANCE: AN AYURVEDIC PERSPECTIVE ON ADVERSE DRUG REACTIONS AND PATIENT SAFETY

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Article Received on
30 July 2025,

Revised on 20 August 2025,
Accepted on 09 Sept. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17213970>

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ABSTRACT

Background: Adverse drug reactions (ADRs) and iatrogenic complications are major global health concerns, forming the foundation of modern pharmacovigilance systems. Ayurveda, though not describing pharmacovigilance as a distinct discipline, embeds safety principles within every stage of *Chikitsa* (treatment), emphasizing prevention of therapeutic errors and safeguarding patient well-being.

Objective: This review aims to critically examine Ayurvedic perspectives on treatment safety with special reference to *Shuddha Chikitsa* and to explore their relevance to contemporary pharmacovigilance and rational therapeutics. **Methods:** A textual and analytical review of classical Ayurvedic compendia (*Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, *Ashtangahridaya*), their commentaries, and modern

pharmacological literature was conducted. Concepts such as *Atiyoga* (overuse), *Ayoga* (underuse), *Mithyayoga* (improper use), *Viruddha Ahara* (incompatible combinations), and *Vyapad* (therapeutic complications) were compared with current classifications of ADRs, drug interactions, contraindications, and iatrogenic risks. **Results:** Ayurveda demonstrates a sophisticated understanding of treatment-related risks, emphasizing individualized care, error prevention, and holistic monitoring. The concept of *Shuddha Chikitsa*, which seeks to eradicate disease without disturbing physiological balance, parallels the core philosophy of modern pharmacovigilance. **Conclusion:** Ayurveda provides an early, integrated framework for treatment safety and rational therapeutics. Its emphasis on preventing adverse outcomes through stage-specific assessment, careful drug-disease matching, and lifestyle considerations highlights its continuing relevance to modern patient safety and pharmacovigilance practices.

KEYWORDS: Ayurveda, Shuddha Chikitsa, Pharmacovigilance, Adverse Drug Reactions, Patient Safety, Vyapad.

INTRODUCTION

Pharmacovigilance, defined as the science and activities related to the detection, assessment, understanding, and prevention of adverse effects of medicines, is a cornerstone of modern medical practice. It safeguards patient safety by identifying risks associated with drug use and ensuring rational therapeutics. While the terminology is modern, the essence of pharmacovigilance is not new.

Ayurveda, the ancient science of life, has long emphasized the safety of treatment, the importance of individualized care, and the prevention of therapy-induced complications. Classical texts consistently caution against improper drug selection, dosage, timing, or patient mismatch, as such errors can transform curable diseases into incurable ones or create new pathologies. Central to this approach is the concept of *Shuddha Chikitsa*—pure and authentic therapy—which eradicates disease without disturbing systemic equilibrium or causing iatrogenic harm.

Against this background, the present paper explores Ayurvedic perspectives on treatment safety, adverse outcomes, and preventive vigilance, positioning them as conceptual parallels to modern pharmacovigilance systems.

Objective: This review aims to critically examine Ayurvedic perspectives on treatment safety with special reference to *Shuddha Chikitsa* and to explore their relevance to contemporary pharmacovigilance and rational therapeutics.

METHODOLOGY

This review is based on a critical analysis of classical Ayurvedic texts alongside modern pharmacological and pharmacovigilance literature. Primary sources such as the *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, and *Ashtangahridaya* were examined, with special attention to sections including *Apasmara Nidana*, *Aturopakramaniya Adhyaya*, *Doshopakramaniya Adhyaya*, and descriptions of *Vyapad* (therapeutic complications). Classical commentaries (*Tikas*) and recent scholarly works in Ayurveda were further consulted to clarify interpretations of *Shuddha Chikitsa* and treatment safety.

The study also reviewed modern definitions of adverse drug reactions (ADRs),

pharmacovigilance categories, and patient safety frameworks. Ayurvedic concepts such as *Atiyoga*, *Ayoga*, *Mithyayoga*, *Viruddha Ahara*, and *Vyapad* were mapped against contemporary classifications of dose-related ADRs, toxicities, interactions, contraindications, and iatrogenic disorders.

Through this comparative and integrative approach, the review identifies conceptual parallels between Ayurveda's safety principles and modern pharmacovigilance, positioning *Shuddha Chikitsa* as a preventive model for minimizing treatment-related risks.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Adverse drug reactions (ADRs) and iatrogenic disorders are significant global health concerns, forming the foundation for modern pharmacovigilance systems that aim to ensure drug safety and minimize treatment-related risks. While pharmacovigilance is a relatively recent discipline in modern medicine, the concept of treatment safety has been integral to Ayurveda since ancient times.

Classical Ayurvedic texts consistently emphasize that true therapy (*Shuddha Chikitsa*) should eradicate disease without generating new complications. Acharyas highlighted the dangers of *Atiyoga* (overuse), *Ayoga* (underuse), *Mithyayoga* (inappropriate use), and *Viruddha Ahara* (incompatible combinations), each of which can lead to *Vyapad*—undesirable treatment outcomes that closely resemble modern descriptions of ADRs. Similarly, warnings regarding improper timing, incorrect patient selection, or unsuitable combinations of drugs and diet indicate a sophisticated awareness of iatrogenic risks.

Despite these insights, Ayurveda does not describe pharmacovigilance as a separate, formal discipline. Instead, safety principles are woven throughout all stages of *Chikitsa*—from diagnosis and treatment planning to administration and completion of therapy. This embedded vigilance reflects Ayurveda's holistic and preventive orientation, offering conceptual parallels to modern pharmacovigilance frameworks.

Central to this understanding is the principle of *Shuddha Chikitsa*—pure and authentic therapy—which safeguards both safety and efficacy of treatment while minimizing the risk of adverse outcomes. Classical texts consistently uphold *Shuddha Chikitsa* as a standard of clinical excellence. In the *Apasmara Nidana* of the *Charaka Samhita*, Acharya Charaka illustrates the risk of *Nidanarthakara Vyadhi* (diseases acting as causative factors for others)

and *Vyadhi Sankara* (compounded pathologies), asserting that authentic therapy eradicates disease fully without creating grounds for future disorders.^[1] In the *Aturopakramaniya Adhyaya* of the *Sushruta Samhita*, Acharya Sushruta emphasizes the significance of accurate diagnosis, correct timing, and proportionate interventions. He warns that even curable diseases may become incurable if mismanaged, further defining *Shuddha Chikitsa* as treatment that pacifies pathology without provoking another. According to him, therapy that alleviates one condition but induces another cannot be considered true treatment.^[2] Likewise, Acharya Vagbhata, in the *Doshopakramaniya Adhyaya* of the *Ashtangahridaya Sutrasthana*, stresses the role of correctly timed interventions, treating *Doshas* in the *Chaya* stage, pacifying those in *Kopa* without aggravating others, and prioritizing the dominant dosha in *Sarva-Dosha Kopa*.^[3]

These classical perspectives clearly establish that the *Lakshana* (hallmark) of *Shuddha Chikitsa* lies not only in *Vyadhi-Nivritti* (eradication of disease) but also in maintaining *Dosha-Dhatu- Samyata* (systemic balance) and preventing *Upadrava* (iatrogenic harm). In modern medicine, iatrogenic disorders—diseases or complications caused by medical interventions—are a major focus of pharmacovigilance, which refers to the science and activities related to the detection, assessment, understanding, and prevention of adverse events or other medicine- or vaccine-related problems.^[4] Ayurveda's emphasis on *Shuddha Chikitsa* demonstrates an ancient parallel to these principles. By defining ideal therapy as that which eradicates disease without inducing new pathologies, classical texts anticipated the risks of overmedication, improper timing, and intervention-related harm.

Thus, Ayurveda inherently incorporates a sophisticated awareness of treatment-related risks, which conceptually parallels the objectives of modern pharmacovigilance and patient safety systems. In this context, the present study was undertaken to critically examine Ayurvedic perspectives on adverse drug reactions, with special reference to *Shuddha Chikitsa*, and to map their relevance to contemporary pharmacovigilance and patient safety practices.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The concept of *Shuddha Chikitsa* represents the highest standard of therapeutic excellence in Ayurveda, emphasizing precision and caution in medical intervention to ensure that therapies restore systemic equilibrium rather than create additional imbalances. Ayurvedic texts highlight that when *Vata* is *Prabala* relative to *Pitta* and *Kapha*, or when all three *Doshas* are simultaneously aggravated, mutual suppression becomes impossible, leading to complications

and disease progression. Thus, *Shuddha Chikitsa* is characterized by its ability to pacify the aggravated *Dosha* without disturbing the remaining *Doshas* (*Shesha Dosha Avirodha*).^[5]

To achieve this therapeutic ideal, Ayurveda stresses rigorous diagnostic assessment, individualized planning, and strict adherence to principles of *Ahara* (diet), *Vihara* (lifestyle), and *Chikitsa*. Even minor errors (*Alpa Apachara*) in these domains may trigger recurrence of disease.^[6] Similarly, the balance between *Samanya* and *Vishesha Siddhanta* is critical, as overuse or underuse of these principles can produce *Dosha-Dhatu Vaishamya*, exacerbating illness.^[7] Conditions like *Hikka* and *Shwasa* exemplify the value of *Anaikantika Chikitsa*—a flexible, patient-centered approach designed to avoid rigid protocols that may provoke other doshas.^[8]

Avasthika Chikitsa, or stage-specific treatment, which emphasizes tailoring interventions according to the disease's progression. Each *Avastha* (stage) demands a context-sensitive therapeutic approach to prevent complications. For instance, in *Grahani Chikitsa*, if the disease stage is marked by *Ruksha* and *Bahukapha*, alternating therapies such as *Rukshana* and *Snehana* are prescribed. Overemphasis on *Rukshana* can lead to *Balahani*, while excessive *Snehana* can cause *Kapha Vriddhi*, both of which worsen the condition.^[9] This stage-specific precision in treatment reflects the essence of *Shuddha Chikitsa*, ensuring that therapy eliminates disease without generating new *Dosha* imbalances or complications.

Timing and dosage (*Matra*) serve as further determinants of safe and effective care. Errors such as *Atiyoga* (overuse) or *Ayoga* (underuse) disrupt the equilibrium of *Dosha*, *Dhatu*, and *Mala*, underscoring the importance of understanding the *Samyak*, *Atiyoga*, and *Ayoga Lakshanas* of all therapeutic procedures within the *Shadvidhopakrama* framework. For instance, in *Jwara Chikitsa*, *Langhana* is prescribed, but only to the extent that it does not deplete the patient's strength. If *Langhana* is administered excessively, it may result in *Balahani* while insufficient use may fail to address the *Jwara* adequately.^[10] Each intervention carries its own indications, duration, and limitations, requiring physicians to apply nuanced judgment in initiating, continuing, or discontinuing treatment.

Ayurvedic Perspectives on Adverse Drug Reactions (ADR)

In Ayurveda, adverse drug reactions (ADR) are well recognized, though expressed through unique concepts of *Dosha*, *Matra*, *Kala* and *Avastha* (stage of disease) etc. Acharyas emphasize that inappropriate selection, administration, or dosage of drugs can lead to

Vyapad—undesirable and harmful outcomes of therapy. These descriptions correlate closely with modern pharmacovigilance concepts, where ADRs are classified based on dose, duration, patient susceptibility, and drug interactions.

1. Dose-Dependent ADRs

Acharya Charaka explicitly warns that even minor deviations in dosage may lead to complications. In *Vamana* and *Virechana Vyapad*, under-dosing in cases of *Bahu Doshavastha* results in *Ayoga Vyapad* (ineffective therapy), producing complications such as *Parisrava*, *Adhmana*, and *Sthambana*. Conversely, over-dosing or administering potent drugs in mild dosha states leads to *Atiyoga Vyapad*, causing conditions like *Parikarthika* and *Jeevadana*.^[11] These resemble modern Type A (dose-related) ADRs, where toxicity results from excessive dosing, or under-dosing compromises therapeutic outcomes.

2. Duration-Related ADRs

Ayurveda also identifies chronicity-induced adverse effects. Continuous or inappropriate long-term use of substances like *Kshara* damages hair, eyes, and reproductive strength, while overuse of *Lavana* results in fatigue, laxity, and debility.^[12] These findings align with modern concepts of cumulative dose toxicity, where prolonged exposure to certain agents leads to systemic or organ-specific damage.

3. Drug-Drug, Drug-Food, and Drug-Disease Interactions

Classical texts provide detailed accounts of harmful interactions, resembling modern studies on pharmacodynamic and pharmacokinetic interactions:

- Drug-Food Interactions: The concept of *Viruddha Ahara* illustrates pharmacodynamic antagonism. For example, *Matsya* (hot potency) taken with *Ksheera* (cold potency) causes *Rakta Dushti* and *Srotorodha*.^[13]
- Drug-Drug Interactions: In *Rasayana* therapy, combining *Shilajatu* with *Kulattha* diminishes its rejuvenative efficacy—an example of antagonistic drug-drug interaction.^[14]
- Drug-Disease Interactions: Inappropriate therapy selection for a given *avastha* often results in complications. For instance, administering *Vamana Dravya* during *Kapha-Anutklishta Taruna Jwara* leads to *Hridroga*, *Shwasa*, *Anaha*, and *Moha*,^[15] resembling contraindicated drug use in modern medicine. Similarly, *Sthambhana* therapy in *Raktapitta* patients with *utklishta dosha* and low *Bala-Mamsa* can aggravate pathology, producing complications such as *Galagraha*, *Putinasya*, *Murcha*, and *Kusta*^[16]—paralleling modern contraindication warnings.

4. Patient-Specific Susceptibility

Ayurveda places strong emphasis on individualized medicine, warning against aggressive therapies in vulnerable populations. Acharya Charaka advises avoiding *Vamana* in *Sukumara*, *Hridrogi*, or patients with *Udavarta*, as complications such as *Hridaya Apakarshana*, *Raktapravrutti*, and severe *Udavarta* may arise. *Vamana* during pregnancy is contraindicated due to risk of *Garbha Vyapath*,^[17] closely resembling modern safety warnings regarding high-risk groups like pregnant women or those with comorbidities.

5. ADRs from Misdiagnosis and Improper Drug Use

Misapplication of therapies also features prominently in Ayurveda. For example, administering *Snehana* in *Urustambha* (mistaken for *Vataroga*) results in *Paadasaada* and *Suptata*.^[18] This mirrors modern ADRs caused by diagnostic errors and inappropriate prescribing.

6. Shuddha Chikitsa as a Preventive Framework

Shuddha Chikitsa serves as Ayurveda's natural pharmacovigilance model. It emphasizes *Vyadhi Shamana* without inducing new pathology, aligning closely with modern goals of drug safety and risk minimization. For instance, in *Grahani Chikitsa*, injudicious use of *Teekshna Agnivaradhaka Dravyas* can provoke *Pitta Kopa* and *Pittaja Pandu*,^[19] illustrating how poor therapeutic planning may generate iatrogenic disease.

CONCLUSION

Ayurveda's therapeutic philosophy demonstrates a sophisticated and integrated understanding of treatment safety, iatrogenic risks, and preventive vigilance, closely paralleling the principles of modern pharmacovigilance. Its detailed descriptions of adverse outcomes—whether arising from dosage errors, inappropriate timing, unsuitable drug-disease matching, or patient-specific vulnerabilities—highlight a holistic commitment to patient safety. Central to this is an emphasis on individualized care, clinical judgment, and prevention of secondary complications.

Although Ayurveda does not present pharmacovigilance as an exclusive, standalone concept, it permeates every stage of *Chikitsa*—from planning and selecting appropriate therapies, to administering them in the right individual, at the right time, and in the right manner, and finally completing treatment in a way that ensures the desired outcome without provoking

new disorders.

The concept of *Shuddha Chikitsa*, which aspires to eradicate disease without disturbing physiological balance, stands as a foundational safety principle. By integrating stage-specific disease assessment, precision in formulation and dosage, and the inseparable roles of *Ahara* (diet) and *Vihara* (lifestyle), Ayurveda provides an early and comprehensive model for drug safety monitoring and rational therapeutics. This underscores its enduring relevance—not only as a traditional medical system but also as a parallel framework to modern pharmacovigilance, dedicated to safeguarding health while achieving effective cure.

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